

**DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL INSTITUTIONAL SYSTEM OF
THE CRYPTO MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN****Ismailova Nasiba Komildjanovna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10608885>**Relevance of the research topic.**

In our country, due to the demands of the time, special attention is paid to the introduction of modern technologies in all areas. For this purpose, on October 5, 2020, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6079 on the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" Strategy was adopted. According to the resolution, over the next 5 years the country plans to increase the export of software products by 10 times and increase the share of the information technology sector in GDP by at least 4%.

The findings of the World Bank's Digital Dividend study show how relevant and important the digital economy is in the development of countries' economies. In particular, 10% increase in Internet speed leads to an increase in the country's GDP. In developed countries this figure is 1.21%, and in developing countries - 1.38%. So, if the Internet speed is doubled, GDP growth can be achieved by 13-14%.

The development of digital technologies ultimately leads to the emergence of intangible assets, that is, non-monetary assets that do not physically exist. For example, if in 1975 the intangible assets of large American corporations amounted to 17 %, then by 2022 this figure has increased to 90 %.

The field of crypto assets has now become one of the completely new and dynamically developing areas of the digital space. In recent years, there has been a steady increase in interest in the crypto-asset market, and the capitalization of this market has reached 1.2 trillion US dollars.

According to the world-famous McKinsey experts, today about 10% of global GDP comes from digital assets, while their development rate is equal to 30% of global economic growth. Digital asset development is like an accelerator.

Analysts from international financial institutions indicate that the rise in prices for cryptocurrencies and the simultaneous influx of funds into related investment products led to the fact that the total volume of assets under management increased to the highest level in a year and a half - up to \$45.3 billion. In terms of investment sources the most money came from Canada and

Germany (87% of the total). Market participants from the US invested less than 9% (\$30 million) of the total amount. 90% of the total funds, \$312 million, were investments in Bitcoin-based instruments (BTC). In addition, \$34 million was channeled into Ethereum (ETH)-based instruments.

In November 2023, several large financial institutions applied to launch their own Bitcoin exchange-traded funds (ETFs), and the first of them could be approved in the first quarter of 2024. According to CryptoQuant analysts, if issuers invest 1% of their assets in these ETFs, the price of Bitcoin could rise to \$50-70 thousand.

The presence of problems within the topic under study.

Currently, there is a clear trend of a general change in views towards this industry, with the governments of many countries becoming increasingly aware of the need for legal regulation of the circulation of crypto-assets. And here it should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan became one of the first countries in the world to pay attention to this area and adopted the relevant regulations. Activities in the field of circulation of crypto assets in our country are legally regulated by the Presidential Decree dated September 2, 2018 "On measures to organize the activities of crypto exchanges in the Republic of Uzbekistan." Based on these decisions, the National Agency for Prospective Projects of the Republic of Uzbekistan was determined to be the authorized body in the field of circulation of crypto-assets.

It should be noted that as early as 2021, internal control rules were adopted for persons operating in the field of crypto-asset turnover, which, in accordance with FATF recommendations, regulate the procedure for conducting "Know Your Client" procedures by crypto exchanges and other service providers. These changes made it possible to create a legal basis for the organization issuing tokens and thereby created the opportunity to introduce a new and innovative tool for attracting investments.

As a result of the work carried out to regulate the sphere of circulation of crypto-assets, the Eurasian Group of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Combating Money Laundering and the Financing of Terrorism received a good assessment in the field of regulation of crypto-assets (FATF Recommendation 15) and "high compliance" during the second round of mutual assessment in the states - members. Only 12 countries in the world have achieved this rating in terms of regulation of this sector. Uzbekistan is one of them.

The measures taken have expanded the range of participants in the national crypto market, which in 2022 is represented by 1 crypto exchange

(“Uznex”) and 4 crypto stores, which became the first legal crypto stores in the CIS and Central Asia. By organizing the activities of service providers, about 40 new jobs were created. In 2022, service providers paid additional state duties and fees to the budget in the amount of 3.8 billion UZS. Rules for the operation of crypto stores were approved in Uzbekistan in October 2022, and by the end of the year, four such organizations received a license.

A new stage in the development of the crypto industry in Uzbekistan began in 2022, when, according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 27, 2022 No. UP-121 “On introducing amendments and additions, as well as recognizing as invalid some acts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” significant changes took place in regulation of the sphere of crypto-circulation. This document, in particular, defined the types of service providers, such as crypto-exchange, mining pool, crypto-depository and crypto-shop.

In 2023, nine licenses were issued to operate service providers in the field of crypto-asset turnover: one crypto-exchange, two crypto-depositories and six crypto-shops. Thus, today in Uzbekistan the number of service providers in the field of crypto-asset turnover has reached fourteen: two crypto-exchanges, two crypto-depositories and ten crypto-shops.

Platforms can operate through an electronic platform or a retail facility (store) - in other words, they have the right to operate both online and offline. Crypto stores also have the right to conduct transactions, including on foreign platforms, to ensure liquidity.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 27, 2022, the National Agency for Prospective Projects established a special regulatory regime in the field of circulation of crypto-assets (“Regulatory Sandbox”), providing for the creation of special organizational and legal conditions for legal entities implementing technologies in the field of circulation of crypto-assets).

Within the framework of the “regulatory sandbox,” legal entities implementing technologies in the field of crypto-asset circulation are provided with special organizational and legal conditions and privileges in legal relations in the process of testing and implementing pilot projects. In particular, participants in the special regime are exempt from paying all types of taxes and mandatory contributions to state trust funds, as well as customs duties (with the exception of customs duties).

The purpose of experimental regulation is to create special conditions for participants in the implementation of pilot projects. The ultimate goal of the “regulatory sandbox” is to, through analyzing the effectiveness of regulatory measures, identify the best results for the country’s economy that can be achieved in the field of crypto-asset turnover.

In 2023, the Agency registered the first three participants in the special “regulatory sandbox” regime. The first participant is United Integrator LLC - UZINFOCOM with a pilot project to introduce NFT certificates based on distributed data registry technology (“blockchain”) for names in the “.UZ” domain zone. To date, more than 420 NFT certificates have been generated and issued within the project.

The second and third participants in the special regime were JSCB Kapitalbank and JSC Octobank with pilot projects for the development and implementation of the banking card product Cryptocard and CRYPTO CARD-UzNEX.

During 2023, as part of pilot projects for the development and implementation of the banking card product “Cryptocard” and “CRYPTO CARD-UzNEX”, more than 90 bank cards were issued, and the cash turnover on them amounted to more than 6 thousand US dollars.

It is worth noting that, along with a number of advantages, crypto-assets have such disadvantages as sale through fraudulent projects, including the issuance of unsubstantiated crypto-assets, financial pyramids, and so on. Similar fraudulent schemes are found in many countries, and Uzbekistan is no exception. Some companies use a pseudo-cryptocurrency that is not supported by anything and is not listed on any crypto exchange. And so, we list the signs of such dubious projects. Among them are the mandatory investment of money to work on the platform, generating income by attracting new participants, concluding an agreement in which the participant assumes all risks, and more. It is worth noting that due to the very low digital literacy of the population, and this area is quite new, only a few truly understand the principle and essence of the circulation of crypto-assets. For others, this is a trap, where they offer to enter and promise a fabulous increase in profits.

On January 19, 2024, Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-899 “On introducing amendments and additions to the Criminal, Criminal Procedure Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Liability” was adopted.

In accordance with this Law, measures of administrative and criminal liability are introduced for the illegal circulation of crypto-assets and illegal mining activities.

Ways to solve problems.

Regarding crypto assets, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, like throughout the world, approaches this conservatively. The Central Bank of Uzbekistan does not consider cryptocurrency to be an asset of value, and their attitude towards it is negative. The Central Bank has repeatedly noted the risks associated with cryptocurrencies. Considering the lack of ability to monitor their turnover, the widespread introduction of cryptoassets creates additional conditions for the development of the shadow economy, the regulator believes. In addition, according to the Central Bank, the lack of collateral and high volatility tied to demand can negatively affect the well-being of the population. In other words, no one can guarantee compensation for losses from rate fluctuations, since cryptocurrencies are not backed by the state. It is necessary to consider a system of limited government guarantees for the use of cryptoassets.

The task of the state is to make regulation simple and understandable, then people will leave the gray zone and enter the legal one. For example, to bring crypto business into the white segment, transactions with such assets were completely exempt from taxation. If you regulate too much, everyone will go into the shadows. People can work through cold wallets and this will lead to the development of the shadow economy.

Scientifically based proposals and recommendations.

Based on the above information, the following recommendations can be made:

firstly, improving the regulatory framework in this area, including strengthening the regulatory framework and harmonization of regulatory documents regulating the circulation of crypto-assets with other regulatory legal acts, ensuring the adoption of regulatory legal acts establishing certain standards liability for violation The established procedure for the circulation of crypto assets and mining is the adoption of departmental regulations governing accounting and mining activities and ensuring their implementation;

secondly, the authorized state body should take measures to expand the institutional base of national crypto market participants, that is, to attract and promote foreign service providers to our country, implement pilot projects for the issuance of investment tokens to attract investments in various sectors of

the economy, to implement specialized international cooperation, it is necessary to further expand international cooperation with organizations and authorized bodies of other countries and carry out extensive advertising work in the field of circulation of crypto-assets.

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